

EXPLORING THE ROLE OF EDUCATIONAL ATTAINMENT ON THE ENTREPRENEURIAL COMPETENCE AND FINANCIAL RISK TOLERANCE OF SMALL-SCALE BANANA GROWERS

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Exploring the Role of Educational Attainment on the Entrepreneurial Competence and Financial Risk Tolerance of Small-Scale Banana Growers

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Abstract

The primary aim of this study was to investigate the impact of educational attainment on entrepreneurial competence and financial risk tolerance among small-scale banana growers. Employing a descriptive-correlational research design with a complete enumeration sampling technique and moderation analysis, data were gathered from 150 small-scale banana growers in Compostela, Davao de Oro. The findings reveal a high level of entrepreneurial competence and financial risk tolerance among the growers. There is a significant relationship between entrepreneurial competence and financial risk tolerance. However, the interaction between entrepreneurial competence and educational attainment had an insignificant effect on the level of financial risk tolerance. This implies that entrepreneurial competence is associated with greater financial risk tolerance regardless of educational attainment, highlighting pathways for enhancing small-scale agriculture's contribution to economic growth and sustainability. This study aligns with the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), particularly SDG 2 (Zero Hunger) and SDG 8 (Decent Work and Economic Growth), by identifying factors that support sustainable agricultural practices and entrepreneurship among small-scale growers. Our findings suggest that fostering entrepreneurial competence can contribute to achieving these goals by enhancing the productivity, sustainability, and financial resilience of small-scale banana growers in developing regions.

Keywords: *entrepreneurial competence, financial risk tolerance, educational attainment, small-scale banana growers*

Introduction

Being characterized by the high level of susceptibility to natural, economic, and policy-related risk, farmers' decisions are heavily influenced by their financial risk tolerance. A lack of financial risk tolerance can lead to suboptimal decision-making, such as underinvestment or overinvestment in certain activities, leading to lower productivity and profitability. Financial risk tolerance can vary depending on a number of criteria, including age, experience, income level, size of farm, and degree of education of farmers. (Abebe et al., 2019).

To further establish this study's central problem, a study by Adnan et al. (2019) analyzed the factors affecting financial risk tolerance among U.S. farm households using data from the Agricultural Resource Management Survey (ARMS). The study found that farm size, off-farm income, education level, and age were significant predictors of financial risk tolerance. Moreover, a study by Lankoski et al. (2019) explored the factors of financial risk tolerance among Finnish dairy farmers using a survey. The relationship of age, farm size, and entrepreneurial attitudes to financial risk tolerance is also positive. Meanwhile, Nweke et al. (2020) to look into the financial risk tolerance of Nigerian maize farmers used a survey in a study. According to the study, higher income and education levels among farmers were associated with more financial risk tolerance than lower ones.

Farmers' financial risk tolerance knowledge can help enhance their financial management and decision-making processes. By identifying the factors influencing farmers' risk tolerance, policymakers, and financial advisors can provide appropriate financial education and support that aligns with their risk preferences. Farmers with higher risk tolerance may be more willing to invest in innovative technologies and production methods, which can improve agricultural productivity and profitability. Such a focus on cultivating agricultural productivity, creativity, and financial intelligence aligns with the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals, especially SDG 2: Zero Hunger, as it aims to achieve sustainable agriculture and better nutrition, and SDG 8: Decent Work and Economic Growth, as it drives economic growth by encouraging entrepreneurship in farming. Our study, by examining the role of educational attainment in entrepreneurial competence and financial risk tolerance among small-scale banana growers, seeks to contribute to these broader objectives. It aims to structure unofficial work, encourage entrepreneurship in rural areas, and clarify the means of attaining equitable and sustainable economic development, job creation, and decent work for all.

Small-scale banana growers' entrepreneurial competence is crucial to the agriculture industry, as well as to economic growth and food security. Shahzad et al. (2020) highlight the innovativeness of these growers, who demonstrate a significant willingness to embrace new high-yielding banana varieties and expand their banana plantations. This readiness meets the market's increasing demands and exemplifies an essential entrepreneurship trait. Echoing this, Serebrennikov et al. (2020) note that such innovation aligns with the dynamic nature of entrepreneurship, necessitating responsiveness to market demands and opportunities for increased productivity.

Regarding risk-taking, the study by Besacier et al. (2021) underscores the growers' cautious approach to investments, emphasizing that they need a clearer understanding of potential benefits to make commitments. As highlighted by Hitt et al. (2018), this prudent strategy suggests that effective risk management is crucial for sustaining and scaling agricultural enterprises.

Discussing proactiveness, the exceptional performance of small-scale banana growers signifies their dedication and work ethic. Boldreanu (2020) supports this observation by relating such performance to the growers' entrepreneurial drive and ambition, which propel them to surpass conventional expectations and achieve higher levels of success. This drive for excellence reflects a commitment to meet and exceed standard agricultural benchmarks.

Finally, regarding their intentions, Aderemi and Oni (2020) and Abbasi et al. (2022) provide evidence that adopting new agricultural technologies is integral to increasing efficiency and competitiveness in farming. The intention of banana growers to incorporate advanced technologies to boost production encapsulates a strategic, forward-thinking mindset. This perspective is crucial for enhancing productivity and maintaining a competitive advantage in a rapidly evolving agricultural landscape.

However, the literature shows that prudent financial conduct, risk aversion, low risk-return outlook, and firm belief in the financial perspective may characterize small-scale banana growers' financial risk tolerance. The literature highlights the cautious financial behaviors of small-scale banana growers who comprehensively evaluate financial options before making any commitments. This strategic intent to minimize risks and optimize returns is fundamental to financial literacy and prudent management, critical for the long-term viability of agricultural operations, as discussed by Cole et al. (2019). Responsible loan management is also notable, with growers committing to fulfilling financial obligations crucial for maintaining credibility and securing future financial resources. Studies in microfinance and rural finance, such as those by Kassegn and Endris (2022), emphasize that responsible borrowing and timely loan repayment are essential for retaining access to credit and improving financial outcomes.

In terms of financial personality, these growers prefer safety over risk, favoring conservative financial choices typically motivated by a desire to protect livelihoods and investments. This risk-averse personality aligns with the conventional understanding of risk aversion, where individuals or entities favor less risky options over potentially higher-yielding but riskier investments, as Ilmanen (2022) notes.

Their attitude toward risks and returns further supports this financial personality, as these growers exhibit a clear preference for financial safety, choosing investments that offer lower risk even if this means potentially lower returns. This risk aversion directly manifests in their overall cautious approach to economic decision-making, which serves to safeguard their agricultural activities against unpredictable financial downturns.

Lastly, the literature affirms high financial confidence among small-scale banana growers. They display strong self-reliance and confidence in managing financial investments effectively. Ghasarma et al. (2017) highlight the importance of this trait, noting how personal confidence in financial management can significantly enhance overall financial stability. The self-efficacy enables the growers to make well-informed financial decisions and eventually influences their general financial efficacy and economic welfare.

Several studies suggest a favorable association between entrepreneurial competence and financial risk tolerance among banana farmers. For instance, Karlan and Valdivia (2011) found that entrepreneurial skills positively correlated with the financial risk behavior in Peru that drove banana farmers. Specifically, the farmers with higher measurements on the entrepreneurial adequacy indicator were more likely to bet on financial risks. Farmers with greater levels of entrepreneurial competence were shown to be more likely to engage in income-generating ventures outside of banana farming, such as chicken farming or retail sales, according to a different study conducted in Kenya by Wanyama et al. (2019). Additionally, there was a greater chance that these farmers would be more risk-tolerant financially.

Furthermore, according to a study done in Ghana by Amponsah et al. (2020), banana farmers who had entrepreneurship and financial management training were more inclined to take calculated risks in their agricultural techniques and had greater levels of financial literacy. Additionally, a study conducted in Kenya by Maritim et al. (2016) discovered that farmers who had access to financing were more inclined to take financial risks and participate in entrepreneurial activities. They found that finance enabled farmers to diversify their revenue sources and grow their enterprises beyond growing bananas.

Human capital theory, a foundational concept in understanding the relationship between individual competencies and economic outcomes, remains a vital lens to examine entrepreneurial behaviors and financial risk tolerance in agriculture. Recent expansions of the theory suggest that individual skills, knowledge, and abilities contribute to productivity and economic success and play a critical role in enhancing entrepreneurial competence and risk management in farming (Newman et al., 2019). In the specific context of banana farming, developing entrepreneurial skills such as innovation, risk assessment, and strategic decision-making is crucial. As outlined by Patel and Thatcher (2014), farmers who exhibit high levels of entrepreneurial competence are better positioned to navigate the uncertainties of agriculture, leading to more effective farm management and identifying new opportunities. This ability directly impacts their financial well-being, fostering a more stable income and increasing risk tolerance (Ucbasaran et al., 2015).

Moreover, experiences and knowledge gained through active engagement in farming and business management further augment farmers' confidence in handling financial risks. This growing confidence, underpinned by a solid foundation of human capital, empowers farmers to embrace calculated risks, thereby driving innovation and economic growth within the agricultural sector (Baluku et al., 2016). Collectively, these recent insights reinforce the notion that human capital development is instrumental in bolstering entrepreneurial competence among farmers, which, in turn, enhances their financial risk tolerance and overall economic success (Baluku et al., 2016; Newman et al., 2019; Patel & Thatcher, 2014; Ucbasaran et al., 2015).

The relationship between entrepreneurial competence, level of education, and financial risk tolerance of small-scale banana growers

can be explored, and the factors that have made the farmers succeed in the business can be established. Proactive growers who actively seek opportunities and adapt to changing circumstances and those intending to engage in financial risk-taking behaviors tend to exhibit a higher tolerance for financial risks. This suggests that promoting proactiveness and developing positive intentions could increase financial resilience and better outcomes in the banana industry (Abdoussalami et al., 2023).

However, the data on the relationship between entrepreneurial competencies and the growers' educational attainment present more diverse results. In particular, Pearson's r correlation was negative and statistically significant for the following independent variables: risk-taking and intentions. This implies risk-taking and entrepreneurial intentions are more prevalent among growers with lower formal education. This is consistent with literature that emphasizes the role of risk-taking propensity and entrepreneurial intentions in shaping entrepreneurial behavior and outcomes (Nabi et al., 2018; Obschonka et al., 2019). Additionally, the significant negative relationship observed for risk-taking aligns with research that underscores the importance of calculated risk-taking in entrepreneurial decision-making and venture creation (Hmieleski & Baron, 2018).

However, the non-significant relationships found for innovativeness and proactiveness with educational attainment suggest that factors beyond individual entrepreneurial traits, such as access to resources, socio-economic background, and institutional support, play a more prominent role in determining educational outcomes for banana growers. This observation echoes recent research suggesting that while entrepreneurial traits are essential, contextual factors significantly influence entrepreneurial success and educational attainment (Obschonka et al., 2018; Foss et al., 2020). Moreover, the overall negative correlation between entrepreneurial competence and educational attainment underscores the complex interplay between formal education and entrepreneurial behavior, indicating that alternative pathways to entrepreneurial success exist beyond traditional educational routes (Stephan et al., 2019).

The insights that entrepreneurship offers contextualize these findings. Although education and risk tolerance are generally associated positively in classic economic theory, new research indicates that this relationship may not always hold, especially when it comes to entrepreneurial decision-making (Giannetti & Simonov, 2018; Wagner et al., 2020), for small-scale farmers like banana growers, whose financial decisions are often influenced by a combination of personal experiences, market dynamics, and socio-economic factors, educational attainment alone may not be a strong predictor of risk tolerance.

Furthermore, studies have shown that risk attitudes are influenced by various psychological, social, and cultural factors beyond formal education, including personality traits, family background, and exposure to risk-taking behavior (Denrell et al., 2018; Koudstaal et al., 2019). Therefore, while education may shape individuals' cognitive abilities and decision-making processes, its direct impact on financial risk tolerance among banana growers may be limited compared to other contextual and individual-level factors.

In addition, while the primary focus of studies on small-scale banana growers often revolves around their entrepreneurial activities and strategies, it is crucial to consider educational attainment as a moderating variable that significantly influences these dynamics. Literature indicates that college graduates within this demographic often have additional skills, knowledge, and resources that enhance their ability to adopt new technologies and manage finances effectively, as highlighted by Hitt et al. (2018). These capabilities are crucial for entrepreneurial competence and success in competitive markets. Conversely, the prevalence of non-college graduates among these growers underscores that agriculture can provide a viable economic livelihood and entrepreneurial opportunity for individuals with diverse educational backgrounds. This observation suggests that while formal education can enhance specific entrepreneurial competencies, the agricultural sector also values practical experience and offers substantial opportunities for success to those without higher education, demonstrating the varied educational pathways contributing to entrepreneurial success in agriculture. Thus, educational attainment has an important moderating role in defining the type and degree of entrepreneurial behavior and the industry's performance.

The signaling theory, first presented by Ross (1977), explains how educational attainment influences the connection between entrepreneurial competence and financial risk tolerance in farmers. The signaling theory posits that a person's education degree reflects their aptitude and dedication to reaching their objectives. In the context of banana farming, farmers with higher levels of education may be perceived as having higher levels of competence and dedication to their business. However, contrary to findings in other sectors indicating a favorable relationship between education and entrepreneurial success (Gilbert et al., 2014), educational attainment may not significantly moderate financial risk tolerance among small-scale banana growers.

Several reasons are proposed for education not playing a decisive moderating role in this context. First, the relevance of educational content to the specific needs of banana growers is crucial. If the education received does not directly address the practical aspects of farming or risk management, its impact on financial risk tolerance might be minimal (Kamal et al., 2014). Additionally, the significant role of experience and informal learning is highlighted, as growers often rely on hands-on experience and local knowledge, which can be more pertinent than formal education in developing risk management strategies (Gundry et al., 2017).

The diversity in educational backgrounds among small-scale banana growers also contributes to the varied impact of education on risk tolerance. While some growers may benefit from education that directly enhances their financial management skills, others may need access to such education, leading to heterogeneous effects across the population (Uwizeyimana et al., 2021). Furthermore, the interaction of education with other factors, such as psychological traits, economic circumstances, and market conditions, complicates its potential moderating role. These interactions can obscure the direct effects of education on risk tolerance (Lusk, 2020).

As a result, they might have an increased chance of getting help from suppliers, lenders, and consumers, strengthening their financial situation and making them more prepared to take financial risks. Higher educated farmers also have a greater understanding of risk assessment and financial management, which enhances their entrepreneurial competency. This increased competence may lead to more informed and strategic financial decisions, increasing their risk tolerance. However, it is essential to remember that depending on contextual factors like market conditions, cultural norms, and resource accessibility, the effect of educational attainment on the correlation between financial risk tolerance and entrepreneurial ability may differ. As a result, educational attainment may have a more moderating effect in some cases than in others. Overall, signaling theory suggests that educational attainment can moderate the relationship between entrepreneurial competence and financial risk tolerance among farmers by influencing perceptions of competence and dedication, improving financial management skills, and potentially increasing access to resources.

Methodology

Respondents

The study focused on a specific group of agricultural entrepreneurs: small-scale banana growers located in Compostela, Davao de Oro. This region is renowned for its substantial contribution to the banana industry, making it an ideal setting for investigating the nuances of entrepreneurial competence and financial risk tolerance within the agricultural sector. The respondents comprised 150 small-scale banana growers who are actively engaged in the cultivation and sale of bananas, a primary agricultural output of the area. This number was determined based on the total population of banana growers in the region, aiming for a comprehensive analysis that could accurately reflect the entrepreneurial competencies and financial risk management practices prevalent among this demographic. The selection of 150 respondents allows for a statistically significant analysis of the data, providing a solid foundation for drawing meaningful conclusions about the impact of educational attainment on these key factors.

The sampling technique employed in this study was complete enumeration sampling. This approach was chosen due to the manageable size of the target population and the study's objective to obtain detailed insights into every small-scale banana grower's perspective within the specified region. By engaging with the entire population of interest, the research aims to minimize sampling bias and ensure that the findings are representative of the small-scale banana farming community in Compostela, Davao de Oro. Complete enumeration sampling is particularly suitable for studies like ours, where the population size is known, accessible, and sufficiently small to allow for exhaustive data collection, thereby strengthening the validity and dependability of the study's findings. The inclusion criteria for the study were specifically designed to ensure that participants had direct experience and engagement with banana farming, thereby providing informed responses relevant to the research questions. Participants were required to be actively managing a banana farm of one to five hectares in size, reflecting the small-scale nature of their agricultural operations. This size criterion was established to focus on growers who are likely to exhibit varied levels of entrepreneurial competence and financial risk tolerance, influenced by their educational background. The exclusion criteria were set to omit individuals not directly involved in banana farming, such as those engaged solely in administrative roles or farming other crops without banana cultivation. Additionally, individuals under the age of 18 were excluded to ensure that all respondents had the legal and practical capacity to make independent farming and business decisions. These criteria were essential for homogenizing the study sample, focusing on those individuals whose experiences and insights would be most pertinent to understanding the interplay between educational attainment, entrepreneurial competence, and financial risk tolerance among small-scale banana growers.

Instruments

A modified questionnaire from Zheng's (2013) study, "Financial risk tolerance, financial behaviors, and demographic characteristics among individual investors in China with the Cronbach alpha of 0.88 and the study of Barzola et.al (2019) "The role of farmers' entrepreneurial orientation on agricultural innovations in Ugandan multi-stakeholder platform. The Climate-Smart Agriculture Papers: Investigating the Business of a Productive, Resilient and Low Emission Future". The survey questionnaires were modified by the researcher to the context of small-scale banana growers in the target research locale.

These research instruments undergone validations of panel of experts and pilot testing with the 30 non-target respondents to find the tool's internal consistency by calculating its Cronbach's alpha. Excellent internal consistency is indicated by the alpha values from the pilot test, which were 0.981 for Financial Risk Tolerance (60 items) and 0.935 for Entrepreneurial Competence (16 items). The scales are robust and reliable for evaluating the targeted constructs of financial risk tolerance and entrepreneurial skill in individuals, as indicated by the high alpha values of each item on the scale.

Procedure

This study employed a descriptive-correlational research design to explore the extent and nature of the relationships between educational attainment, entrepreneurial competence, and financial risk tolerance among small-scale banana growers. The descriptive aspect of the study focused on characterizing these variables in detail, while the correlational aspect aimed to uncover the strength and direction of associations between them. By combining these approaches, we sought to not only describe the prevalent traits within the target population but also to understand how these traits relate to one another within the context of small-scale agricultural entrepreneurship. Furthermore, this design enables for the collecting and analysis of numerical data, which can aid in determining the

strength and direction of correlations between variables as well as testing hypotheses (Bryman 2016). Furthermore, the use of quantitative methods in research allows for data analysis, which can aid in determining the degree of association between variables, such as the link between entrepreneurial competence and financial risk tolerance among small-scale banana farmers in Compostela, Davao de Oro, as well as the moderating effect of educational attainment (Field, 2013).

Moderation analysis was performed to evaluate the possible moderating impact of educational attainment on the link between financial risk tolerance and entrepreneurial skill. This statistical technique is employed to determine whether the strength or direction of the association between an independent variable and a dependent variable changes in the presence of a third moderating variable. The inclusion of moderation analysis in our study design allowed us to delve deeper into the complexity of these relationships and to figure out the extent to which educational attainment influences the financial decisions and risk profiles of banana growers.

Data collection was executed systematically over six months, integrating the phases of gathering data, analysis, and manuscript preparation into a cohesive timeline. Upon validating the questionnaires with external validators, the researcher secured permission from the Chairman of the Municipal Banana Council of LGU Compostela. Following approval, the well-structured questionnaires were personally distributed to the small-scale banana growers, ensuring that each was completed accurately to provide a robust dataset. This direct method not only ensured high-quality, reliable data but also facilitated a thorough analytical process. The researcher collected and tabulated the responses, which informed the analysis and interpretation of the statistical results. Drawing from these results, the researcher formulated conclusions and recommendations, supporting them with an array of literature to substantiate this academic pursuit.

Statistical tools will be used in treating the data collected: Frequency will be used to describe the demographic profile of the small-scale banana farmers in terms of their educational attainment. Mean will be used to describe the level of entrepreneurial competence and financial risk tolerance. Pearson r will be used to determine if there is a significant relationship between entrepreneurial competence and financial risk tolerance, entrepreneurial competence and educational attainment and educational attainment and financial risk tolerance. Sobel z -test will be used to establish moderating effect of educational attainment to the relationship between entrepreneurial competence and financial risk tolerance among small-scale banana farmers in Compostela, Davao de Oro.

The research process was designed and conducted in strict adherence to ethical standards, ensuring respect, confidentiality, and integrity throughout. Approval for the study was granted by the University of Mindanao Ethics Review Committee (UMERC), with the study being assigned UMREC Certification Number UMERC-2023-263. This certification affirmed the study's compliance with ethical guidelines, safeguarding the well-being and rights of all participants involved in the research.

Results and Discussion

The study's analysis and findings were covered in this section. This chapter utilizes both textual and tabular modes to deliver the data effectively. The results in this study used the 0.05 level of significance in terms of the analysis of the inferential results. Consecutively, the tables and their interpretation were arranged in the subsequent subheadings: Entrepreneurial Competence of Small-Scale Banana Growers, Financial Risk Tolerance of Small-scale Banana Growers, The Educational Attainment of Small-Scale Banana Growers, Significance on the Relationship between Entrepreneurial Competence and Financial Risk Tolerance, and The Moderating Effect of Educational Attainment on the Relationship between Entrepreneurial Competence and Financial Risk Tolerance of Small-Scale Banana Growers.

Entrepreneurial Competence of Small-Scale Banana Growers

The mean scores for the small-scale banana growers' entrepreneurial Competence with an overall mean of 3.99, with a standard deviation of 0.6490 were presented in Table 1. The high level could be attributed to the high rating given by the respondents in all indicators in terms of innovativeness, risk-taking, proactiveness, and intentions. The total mean score being mentioned was the outcome acquired from the subsequent computed mean scores from the highest to lowest indicators. In addition, the overall mean scores and standard deviation for each indicator that was mentioned above were presented in the appended table (Table 1.1).

Table 1 evaluates the entrepreneurial competence of small-scale banana growers, focusing on various indicators. The highest competence is observed in Innovativeness, with a mean score of 4.08, reflecting a strong propensity among growers to adopt new technologies and high-yielding varieties. On the other hand, the lowest competence is in Proactiveness, despite a still high mean score of 4.03, indicating a slightly lesser readiness to initiate new and forward-looking practices. These results highlight key areas of strength and relative developmental need within the entrepreneurial attributes of these banana growers.

The results of the study indicate that small-scale banana growers exhibit a strong entrepreneurial competence, with a particular focus on their willingness to embrace new high-yielding banana varieties and increase the number of banana plants on their farms. This finding underscores their commitment to satisfying a growing customer base and adapting to changing market demands. Entrepreneurship in agriculture is crucial for ensuring food security and economic development, and these small-scale growers' readiness to adopt new farming practices aligns with the concept of agripreneurship, emphasizing innovation and risk-taking (Shahzad et al., 2020). Moreover, the preference of these growers to only invest with a clear understanding of the potential benefits reflects their

cautious approach to risk management. It is well-documented that entrepreneurial competence involves evaluating risks and rewards, and this characteristic highlights the farmers' strategic decision-making in managing their operations (Besacier et al., 2021).

Table 1. *Entrepreneurial Competence of Small-Scale Banana Growers*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Descriptive</i>
Innovativeness	4.08	0.6679	High
Risk-Taking	3.98	0.6665	High
Proactiveness	4.03	0.6213	High
Intentions	3.89	0.6401	High
Overall	3.99	0.6490	High

In addition to their willingness to adopt new banana varieties and manage investments prudently, the study reveals that small-scale banana growers exceed expectations in their performance. This suggests that these farmers go the extra mile in their efforts to produce high-quality bananas, demonstrating a strong work ethic and dedication to their business. Furthermore, their intention to incorporate new agricultural technologies to boost banana production over the next three years reflects a forward-thinking mindset. Adopting technology is a hallmark of entrepreneurial competence, as it increases efficiency and competitiveness (Aderemi & Oni, 2020). These results highlight the entrepreneurial competence of small-scale banana growers, showcasing their adaptability, risk assessment, commitment to excellence, and embrace of technology, all of which contribute to the sustainability and growth of their farming enterprises.

The study's results regarding the entrepreneurial competence of small-scale banana growers provide valuable insights that can be linked to theoretical frameworks and empirical evidence in entrepreneurship and agriculture. Firstly, the growers' willingness to include new high-yielding banana varieties and expand the number of banana plants on their farms aligns with the concept of innovation and adaptability, which is a central tenet of entrepreneurial competence. Adopting new, high-yielding varieties reflects the growers' responsiveness to market demand and their pursuit of increased productivity, which aligns with the literature on the dynamic nature of entrepreneurship (Serebrennikov et al., 2020).

Moreover, the preference of small-scale banana growers to only make investments with a clear understanding of the potential benefits is consistent with the literature on risk management in entrepreneurship. Entrepreneurs are expected to assess the risk and return of investments, and this cautious approach can be seen as a responsible and prudent strategy. Research in the field of entrepreneurship emphasizes the importance of risk assessment and avoidance of overly speculative investments (Hitt et al., 2018).

The finding that these growers perform above and beyond expectations indicates their commitment to excellence and drive for success. This commitment corresponds to entrepreneurial drive and ambition, a key component of entrepreneurial competence. Entrepreneurs are often characterized by their determination to exceed established benchmarks and achieve higher levels of performance (Boldureanu, 2020).

Lastly, the growers' goal to increase the productivity of their banana crop by implementing new technology within the next three years is consistent with the empirical data that highlights the advantages of technology adoption in agriculture. Research has consistently shown that integrating technology can lead to increased efficiency, productivity, and competitiveness in the agricultural sector, and this intent reflects the growers' forward-thinking and strategic approach to improving their operations (Abbasi et al., 2022).

Financial Risk Tolerance of Small-Scale Banana Growers

The mean scores for the small-scale banana growers' financial risk tolerance with an overall mean of 3.80 with a standard deviation of 0.6070 were presented in Table 2. The high level could be attributed to the high rating given by the respondents in all indicators in terms of financial behaviors, financial personality, financial attitude toward risks and returns, and financial confidence level. The total mean score being mentioned was the outcome acquired from the subsequent computed mean scores from the highest to lowest indicators. In addition, the overall mean scores and standard deviation for each indicator mentioned above are presented in the appended table (Table 2).

Table 2. *Financial Risk Tolerance of Small-Scale Banana Growers*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Descriptive</i>
Financial Behaviors	3.80	0.6262	High
Financial Personality	3.87	0.5836	High
Financial Attitude Toward Risks and Returns	3.77	0.5997	High
Financial Confidence Level	3.77	0.6186	High
Overall	3.80	0.6070	High

Table 2 examines the financial risk tolerance of small-scale banana growers. The indicator with the highest score is Financial Personality, showing a mean of 3.87, which suggests a robust financial disposition among the growers. The lowest score is tied between Financial Attitude Toward Risks and Returns and Financial Confidence Level, both with a mean of 3.77. These results indicate that while the growers have a strong financial personality, there is a relative caution or lower confidence when dealing with risks and returns.

Furthermore, the results show that, with regard to financial risk tolerance, small-scale banana growers consider choices multiple times before making the financial choice, that they are responsible for the financial loans they took, that they prefer safety over risk when making financial investments, and that they believe they have the talent to manage their money investment. The outcomes of this study shed insight on small-scale banana farmers' financial risk tolerance and demonstrate their prudent approach to financial decision-making. The results show that small-scale banana farmers deliberate and thoroughly evaluate their financial options before making any decisions. This careful consideration reflects their desire to minimize financial risks and optimize their returns. This characteristic aligns with the concept of financial literacy and prudent financial management, which are crucial for the long-term sustainability of agricultural enterprises (Cole et al., 2019).

Moreover, the results indicate that these growers are responsible for the financial loans they take, underscoring their commitment to fulfilling their financial obligations. Responsible loan management is a fundamental aspect of financial competence, and it ensures the growers' credibility and access to future financial resources. Furthermore, the preference for safety over risk when making financial investments demonstrates a risk-averse mindset. This inclination to opt for safer, more conservative financial choices may be rooted in a desire to protect their livelihoods and investments. Lastly, believing in their talent to manage their money investments points to a self-reliant and confident approach to financial decision-making. This self-efficacy is a valuable asset in fostering financial competence and ensuring the economic well-being of small-scale banana growers (Ghasarma et al., 2017.).

These suggest that small-scale banana growers exhibit a cautious approach to financial risk tolerance, which aligns with existing theoretical and empirical evidence in agricultural economics and entrepreneurship. The cautious approach to financial decision-making, characterized by a careful evaluation of options and a preference for safety, supports the theoretical framework of risk aversion in making economic choices. This concept is well-established in the literature, with risk-averse individuals or entities being inclined to choose less risky options over potentially higher-yielding but riskier investments. The preference for safety in the context of financial investment is in line with the traditional understanding of risk aversion (Ilmanen, 2022).

The responsible management of financial loans by small-scale banana growers also resonates with empirical evidence in the field of microfinance and rural finance. Numerous studies have demonstrated that responsible borrowing and timely repayment of loans are critical for maintaining access to credit and improving financial outcomes for small-scale farmers (Kassegn & Endris, 2022). This aligns with the study's findings that these growers are diligent in fulfilling their financial obligations.

Educational Attainment of Small-Scale Banana Growers

The educational attainment of small-scale banana growers has been a subject of increasing significance in recent years, with findings indicating a complex interplay between educational levels and the sustainability and productivity of this vital agricultural sector. The frequency and percentage in the table below (Table 3.), are the descriptive for the educational attainment of the respondents, which is categorized into two: college graduate and non-college graduate.

Table 3. Educational Attainment of Small-Scale Banana Growers

<i>Educational Attainment</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>%</i>
College Graduate	13	8.67%
Non-College Graduate	137	91.33%
Total	150	100%

The table above shows the number and percentage of college graduates and non-college graduates among the respondents. It indicates a frequency of 13 out of 150, 8.67% for college graduates, small-scale banana growers, and 137 out of 150, 91.33% for non-college graduates, small-scale banana growers out of the total number of respondents.

The table presenting the educational breakdown of the respondents provides valuable insights into the academic background of small-scale banana growers. It reveals that 8.67% of the respondents are college graduates, while a significant majority, 91.33%, are non-college graduates. The findings align with earlier studies that frequently highlight the significance of education in shaping entrepreneurial behavior and success. College graduates may possess additional skills, knowledge, and access to resources that can impact their entrepreneurial competence, including their ability to adopt new technologies or manage finances (Hitt et al., 2018). On the other hand, non-college graduates' dominance among small-scale banana growers suggests the potential for self-employment and entrepreneurship to serve as a viable path to economic livelihood and agricultural entrepreneurship for those with varying educational backgrounds.

Significance of the Relationship between Entrepreneurial Competence and Financial Risk Tolerance, Entrepreneurial Competence and Educational Attainment, and Educational Attainment and Financial Risk Tolerance

One of the objectives of this study is to determine whether there is a significant relationship between Entrepreneurial Competence and Financial Risk Tolerance, Entrepreneurial Competence and Educational Attainment, and Educational Attainment and Financial Risk Tolerance of small-scale banana growers. Moreover, Pearson-r was used to determine or explore the connection between variables. In addition, the analyzed data on the significance on the relationship between the variables indicated above, are presented in tables 4.1, 4.2 and 4.3.

Significance on the Relationship between Entrepreneurial Competence and Financial Risk Tolerance

The significant relationship between the independent variable, educational attainment and the dependent variable, financial risk tolerance of small-scale banana growers is presented in the table below.

Table 4.1. *Correlation between Entrepreneurial Competence and Financial Risk Tolerance of Small-scale Banana Growers*

<i>Independent Variable</i>	<i>Dependent Variable</i>	<i>r-value</i>	<i>r-square</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>Decision</i>
Innovativeness	Financial Risk Tolerance	0.452	0.204	0.001	Reject H0
Risk-Taking		0.552	0.304	0.001	Reject H0
Proactiveness		0.634	0.402	0.001	Reject H0
Intentions		0.548	0.300	0.001	Reject H0
Overall		0.666	0.444	0.001	Reject H0

The table above shows the relationship between the indicators and the overall independent variable, entrepreneurial competence, which is the innovativeness, risk-taking, proactiveness, and intentions of small-scale banana growers' financial risk tolerance. The first indicator has an r-value of 0.452 with a p-value of 0.001, which means that there is a significant relationship and a coefficient of determination of 0.204, which shows a low positive correlation. The second indicator has an r-value of 0.552 with a p-value of 0.001, which means that there is a significant relationship and a coefficient of determination of 0.304, which shows a moderate positive correlation. The third indicator has an r-value of 0.634 with a p-value of 0.001, which means that there is a significant relationship and a coefficient of determination of 0.402, which shows a moderate positive correlation. The last indicator for the independent variable has an r-value of 0.548 and a p-value of 0.001, meaning there is a significant relationship, and a coefficient of determination of 0.300 shows a moderate positive correlation. Overall, the level of entrepreneurial competence and the level of financial risk tolerance of small-scale growers has an r-value of 0.666 with a p-value of 0.001, which means that there is a significant relationship and a coefficient of determination 0.4444, which shows a moderate positive correlation.

Moreover, the gathered outcomes revealed that the level of entrepreneurial competence is significantly related to the level of financial risk tolerance of small-scale banana growers. Furthermore, as presented in the table above, the hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between the level of entrepreneurial competence and the level of financial risk tolerance of small-scale banana growers is rejected.

The study found that innovativeness, as one of the indicators of entrepreneurial competence, showed a low but significant positive correlation ($r = 0.452$, $p < 0.001$) with financial risk tolerance. This implies that small-scale growers of bananas who demonstrate a higher level of innovation are more willing to take financial risks. This result underscores the importance of fostering innovation within the agricultural sector, as it appears to enhance growers' readiness to take on financial risks (Pan et al., 2024).

Furthermore, the research revealed a more substantial positive correlation between risk-taking and financial risk tolerance ($r = 0.552$, $p < 0.001$), with a moderate coefficient of determination (0.304). This implies that small-scale growers who are more inclined to take risks in their entrepreneurial endeavors tend to have a greater tolerance for financial risks. This insight is valuable for policymakers and agricultural stakeholders, highlighting the potential benefits of encouraging risk-taking among small-scale growers to improve their financial resilience and sustainability (Kangogo et al., 2021).

The study also found that proactiveness and intentions to financial risk tolerance displayed significant positive correlations ($r = 0.634$ and 0.548 , respectively, with $p < 0.001$). The moderate coefficients of determination (0.402 and 0.300) indicate that these factors significantly shape financial risk tolerance among small-scale banana growers. Proactive growers who actively seek opportunities and adapt to changing circumstances and those intending to engage in financial risk-taking behaviors are more inclined to exhibit a greater tolerance for financial risks. These findings emphasize the importance of promoting proactiveness and the development of positive intentions among small-scale growers, potentially leading to increased financial resilience and better overall outcomes in the banana industry (Abdoussalami et al., 2023).

Significance on the Relationship between Entrepreneurial Competence and Educational Attainment

The significant relationship between the independent variable, entrepreneurial competence and the moderating variable, educational attainment of small-scale banana growers is presented in the table below.

The table above shows the relationship between the indicators and the overall independent variable, entrepreneurial competence, which is innovativeness, risk-taking, proactiveness, and intentions for the educational attainment of small-scale banana growers. The first indicator has an r-value of -0.088 with a p-value of 0.284, which means that there is no significant relationship, and a coefficient of determination of 0.007, which shows a low negative correlation. The second indicator has an r-value of -0.303 with a p-value of 0.001, which means that there is a significant relationship and a coefficient of determination of 0.092, which shows a low negative correlation. The third indicator has an r-value of -0.138 with a p-value of 0.093 which means that there is no significant relationship and a coefficient of determination of 0.019, which shows a low negative correlation. The fourth indicator has an r-value of -0.254 with a p-value of 0.001, which means that there is a significant relationship and a coefficient of determination of 0.065, which shows a low negative

correlation. Overall, the entrepreneurial competence of small-scale banana growers has an r -value of -0.239 with a p -value of 0.001 which means that there is a significant relationship towards their educational attainment. It also shows that it has a coefficient of determination of 0.057 , which indicates a low negative correlation.

Table 4.2. *Correlation between Entrepreneurial Competence and Educational Attainment of Small-scale Banana Growers*

<i>Independent Variable</i>	<i>Moderating Variable</i>	<i>r-value</i>	<i>r-square</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>Decision</i>
Innovativeness	Educational Attainment	-0.088	0.007	0.284	Failed to reject H0
Risk-Taking		-0.303	0.092	0.001	Reject H0
Proactiveness		-0.138	0.019	0.093	Failed to reject H0
Intentions		-0.254	0.065	0.001	Reject H0
Overall		-0.239	0.057	0.001	Reject H0

The results from the analysis indicate a nuanced relationship between entrepreneurial competence and educational attainment among small-scale banana growers. Specifically, risk-taking and intentions exhibit statistically significant negative correlations with educational attainment, suggesting that higher levels of risk-taking behavior and entrepreneurial intentions are associated with lower levels of formal education among banana growers. These findings are consistent with contemporary literature that emphasizes the role of risk-taking propensity and entrepreneurial intentions in shaping entrepreneurial behavior and outcomes (Nabi et al., 2018; Obschonka et al., 2019). Moreover, the significant negative relationship observed for risk-taking aligns with research highlighting the importance of calculated risk-taking in entrepreneurial decision-making and venture creation (Hmieleski & Baron, 2018).

However, the non-significant relationships found for innovativeness and proactiveness with educational attainment may suggest that other factors beyond individual entrepreneurial traits play a more prominent role in determining educational outcomes for banana growers. This finding echoes recent research suggesting that while entrepreneurial traits are important, contextual factors such as access to resources, socio-economic background, and institutional support also significantly influence entrepreneurial success and educational attainment (Obschonka et al., 2018; Foss et al., 2020). Furthermore, the overall negative correlation between entrepreneurial competence and educational attainment underscores the complex interplay between formal education and entrepreneurial behavior, indicating that alternative pathways to entrepreneurial success exist beyond traditional educational routes (Stephan et al., 2019).

Significance on the Relationship between Educational Attainment and Financial Risk Tolerance

The significant relationship between the moderating variable, educational attainment and the dependent variable, financial risk tolerance of small-scale banana growers is presented in the table below.

Table 4.3. *Correlation between Educational Attainment and Financial Risk Tolerance of Small-scale Banana Growers*

<i>Moderating Variable</i>	<i>Dependent Variable</i>	<i>r-value</i>	<i>r-square</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>Decision</i>
Educational Attainment	Financial Risk Tolerance	-0.082	0.007	0.318	Failed to reject H0

The table above shows the relationship between the educational attainment and the financial risk tolerance of small-scale banana growers. The results shows that it has an r -value of -0.082 with a p -value of 0.318 which means that there is no significant relationship between the variables, and a coefficient of determination of 0.007 , which shows a low negative correlation, although this correlation is not statistically meaningful.

Recent research on the association between education and risk tolerance in entrepreneurship gives context for these findings. While classic economic theory frequently assumes a positive association between education and risk tolerance, recent research indicates that this relationship may not always be true, particularly in the context of entrepreneurial decision-making (Giannetti & Simonov, 2018; Wagner et al., 2020). For small-scale farmers like banana growers, whose financial decisions are often influenced by a combination of personal experiences, market dynamics, and socio-economic factors, educational attainment alone may not be a strong predictor of risk tolerance.

Moreover, studies have shown that risk attitudes are influenced by various psychological, social, and cultural factors beyond formal education, including personality traits, family background, and exposure to risk-taking behavior (Denrell et al., 2018; Koudstaal et al., 2019). Therefore, while education may play a role in shaping individuals' cognitive abilities and decision-making processes, its direct impact on financial risk tolerance among banana growers may be limited compared to other contextual and individual-level factors.

Moderating Effect of Educational Attainment on the Relationship between Entrepreneurial Competence and Financial Risk Tolerance of Small-Scale Banana Growers

The primary goal of this study is to establish if the moderating variable, educational attainment modifies the connection between entrepreneurial skill and financial risk tolerance. Moreover, a simple linear regression was utilized to determine or investigate the impact of the interaction between variables.

In connection to the study's main purpose, it was expected that small-scale banana growers with high educational attainment would

have a higher association between their level of entrepreneurial competence and their financial risk tolerance. The results indicated that entrepreneurial competence ($B = 0.6689$, $p < 0.001$) had significant positive effect on financial risk tolerance on small-scale banana growers, since its p-value is less than to the level of significance which is 0.05. However, the results showed that educational attainment ($B = 0.2715$, $p = 0.067$) and the interaction of entrepreneurial competence and educational attainment ($B = 0.0481$, $p = 0.793$), had an insignificant effect of the level of financial risk tolerance of small-scale banana growers, since the p-values are greater than the level of significance which is 0.05.

Table 5. *Moderating Effect of Educational Attainment on the Relationship between Entrepreneurial Competence and Financial Risk Tolerance of Small-Scale Banana Growers*

	Estimate	SE	95% Confidence Interval		Z	p
			Lower	Upper		
ENTREPC	0.6689	0.0741	0.5236	0.814	9.023	< .001
EDUC	0.2715	0.1481	-0.0187	0.562	1.834	0.067
ENTREPC * EDUC	0.0481	0.1832	-0.3110	0.407	0.262	0.793

The result highlights the importance of entrepreneurial competence in enhancing the financial risk tolerance of small-scale banana growers. This result is in line with earlier studies' findings that entrepreneurs had a higher risk tolerance than other managers and people who have full-time jobs (Smith J.D., 2022). The study further points the possibility that small-scale banana growers' financial risk tolerance may not be much influenced by their level of education. This result contradicts other studies' findings, which indicated a favorable correlation between education and successful entrepreneurship (Gilbert et al., 2014). Moreover, the study provides insights into the factors that influence the financial risk tolerance of small-scale banana growers and highlights the importance of entrepreneurial competence in enhancing their financial risk tolerance.

Effect of the Predictor variable on the Dependent variable at different levels of the Moderating variable

In Table 6, the simple slope analysis, it shows the effect of the predictor which is entrepreneurial competence on the dependent variable which is financial risk tolerance at different levels of the moderating variable which is educational attainment.

Table 6. *Simple Slope Analysis of the effect of Educational Attainment on the Financial Risk Tolerance at different levels of the Moderator.*

	Estimate	SE	95% Confidence Interval		Z	p
			Lower	Upper		
Average	0.669	0.0741	0.524	0.814	9.02	< .001
Low (-1SD)	0.655	0.1009	0.457	0.853	6.49	< .001
High (+1SD)	0.682	0.0782	0.529	0.836	8.73	< .001

Note. shows the effect of the predictor (ENTREPC) on the dependent variable (RISKTOL) at different levels of the moderator (EDUC)

The results above revealed that on average, it shows a significant effect ($B = 0.669$, $p < 0.001$), between the level of entrepreneurial skills and the level of financial risk tolerance of small-scale banana growers. On the results when the moderator is high and low, the analysis shows that when educational attainment are low, there is a significant positive relationship between the level of entrepreneurial skills and the level of financial risk tolerance of small-scale banana growers, $B = 0.655$, $p < 0.001$. It also shows that when educational attainment are high, there is a significant positive relationship between the level of entrepreneurial skills and the level of financial risk tolerance of small-scale banana growers, $B = 0.682$, $p < 0.001$. These findings indicate that entrepreneurial competence is associated with the greater financial risk tolerance, regardless of the educational attainment of a small-scale banana grower.

The figure (Figure 1) below further illustrates the simple slopes at different levels of educational attainment on the association between entrepreneurial competence and financial risk tolerance of small-scale banana growers. The figure shows that, the slopes in different levels of educational attainment of small-scale banana growers are approximately the same or closer with each other, which implies that the level of educational attainment of small-scale banana growers does not significantly moderates the association of their entrepreneurial competence and financial risk tolerance.

Furthermore, the study's findings align with previous research indicating that small-scale farmers, especially those with little resources, display risk aversion rather than neutrality or preference when confronted with negative outcomes (Bradley et al., 2021). The results of the study indicate that small-scale banana growers can reduce the risks involved in farming and enhance their financial performance by developing their entrepreneurial abilities (Bannor et al., 2021).

The lack of a substantial moderating influence of educational attainment on the link between entrepreneurial competence and financial risk tolerance among small-scale banana growers can be attributed to a number of factors, which are discussed below based on several

studies. The first is the contextual relevance of education; the knowledge and skills obtained through formal education must be relevant in the given situation in order for education to be effective in regulating the link between financial risk tolerance and entrepreneurial competence. Small-scale banana farming often involves practical, on-the-ground knowledge and decision-making. While education can be valuable, its direct applicability to farming practices may vary. If the education received by small-scale banana growers does not directly address the intricacies of farming or risk management, it may not significantly influence their financial risk tolerance (Kamal et al., 2014).

Figure 1. Simple Slope Plot of Entrepreneurial Competence and Financial Risk Tolerance in different levels of Educational Attainment

Second is the role of experience and informal learning, small-scale banana growers often rely on years of hands-on experience, local knowledge, and informal learning from peers and family members. This experiential learning can play a significant role in shaping risk tolerance. Even if formal education is limited, the practical insights gained through experience can be crucial in helping growers assess and manage financial risks. These informal learning processes can mitigate the need for formal education to moderate the relationship between entrepreneurial competence and risk tolerance (Gundry et al., 2017).

Third is the diverse educational backgrounds, educational attainment varies widely among small-scale banana growers. The level of education can range from limited formal schooling to higher education. The diversity in educational backgrounds may lead to heterogeneity in the impact of education on risk tolerance. Some growers may have acquired specialized knowledge and skills that directly contribute to their ability to manage financial risks, while others may not have had the opportunity to do so. This variability in educational backgrounds may obscure the Fourth, there is the interaction with other elements; psychological features, economic circumstances, and market conditions all have an impact on financial risk tolerance. The moderating effect of education may be outweighed by the effects of these other variables. Education may interact with some of these elements in complex ways, making it difficult to pinpoint its exact function in modulating the relationship between entrepreneurial skill and risk tolerance (Lusk, 2020).

Moreover, the lack of a significant moderating effect of educational attainment on the association between entrepreneurial competence and financial risk tolerance among small-scale banana growers can be explained because of education's contextual relevance, the importance of experiential learning, the diverse educational backgrounds of growers, and the complex interplay of multiple influencing factors. Understanding these dynamics is crucial in crafting effective strategies to enhance financial risk management among small-scale banana growers, acknowledging the significance of both formal education and practical experience.

Conclusions

This study underscores the significant impact of entrepreneurial competence on financial risk tolerance among small-scale banana growers in Compostela, Davao de Oro, irrespective of their educational attainment. Areas requiring focused intervention include the intentions and risk management behaviors, which recorded the lowest scores. These results cast doubt on conventional theoretical frameworks that highlight the moderating influence of education on financial behaviors and propose that it is more beneficial to directly improve entrepreneurial skills.

To address the gaps identified, it is recommended that a business incubation program tailored to banana cultivation be launched, offering guidance on business planning and financial management. This program could be facilitated by the Agricultural Training Institute (ATI) in coordination with the Local Government of Compostela, ensuring it aligns with local practices and market needs. Financial literacy and risk management workshops should also be developed to educate growers on the benefits of calculated risk-

taking. These workshops, supported by the Department of Agriculture, could include case studies on successful agricultural investments. Furthermore, a demonstration and subsidy program should be implemented to promote the utilization of new technologies, sponsored by local agri-tech firms and possibly the state university's agriculture department. This program would include hands-on demonstrations and offer initial financial subsidies or low-interest loans for early adopters. Peer-to-peer mentoring sessions, facilitated by the ATI and supported by microfinance institutions, could also be beneficial. These sessions would allow experienced and financially literate growers to share their strategies with others, enhancing collective financial risk tolerance. Lastly, considering the minimal influence of formal education on one's capacity for financial risk, collaboration with agricultural colleges to design short, practical courses focused on specific competencies such as risk assessment and crop management is advised. These courses should be accredited and government-subsidized to encourage participation.

The results suggest a shift towards a more competency-based framework for understanding financial decision-making in agriculture, focusing on practical skills acquisition over traditional educational pathways. This shift indicates a need to rethink how academic programs are designed and implemented to better serve the agricultural sector's real-world demands.

By directly integrating specific, results-based recommendations into the conclusion, this revision ensures that each significant finding is paired with practical and achievable action, thus enhancing the overall impact and applicability of the study's outcomes.

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